

TOWARD A GLOBAL CATALOG OF ~200 M LUNAR IMPACT CRATERS. Wei Zuo¹, Wangli Chen¹, Jianjun Liu¹ and Chunlai Li¹, ¹Key Laboratory of Lunar and Deep Space Exploration, National Astronomical Observatories, Chinese Academy of Sciences, Beijing 100101, China (zuowei@nao.cas.cn, chenwl@nao.cas.cn, liujj@nao.cas.cn, licl@nao.cas.cn).

Introduction: Impact craters dominate the lunar surface and record the impact history of the Earth–Moon system [1]. Global crater catalogs have been developed for kilometer-scale craters, providing fundamental constraints on lunar surface ages and impact flux [2,3]. However, systematic inventories of smaller craters remain limited despite their importance for understanding small impactor populations and surface modification processes [4]. Craters with diameters of a few hundred meters represent a key size range for investigating the transition between primary crater populations and smaller-scale impact processes. Developing a global catalog of ~200 m lunar impact craters therefore provides an important foundation for studies of lunar impact history and small-crater populations.

Catalog Construction: We are constructing a new global catalog of lunar impact craters with diameters around ~200 m [Fig.1] using high-resolution lunar orbital imagery [5] combined with automated detection algorithms [6] and quality-control procedures. The catalog records crater locations and diameter measurements and provides near-global coverage of the lunar surface. The current version of the **catalog contains more than 10.6 million detected lunar impact craters**, making it one of the largest datasets of sub-kilometer craters compiled to date.

This dataset significantly expands the available inventory of small lunar craters and enables systematic analyses of crater populations at scales that were previously difficult to study globally.

Preliminary Characteristics: Initial examination of the catalog reveals substantial spatial variability in crater densities across the lunar surface. Differences between maria and highland terrains likely reflect variations in geological resurfacing processes and surface ages [7,8]. The large number of detected craters also enables improved characterization of crater size–frequency distributions around diameters of a few hundred meters [9]. These results highlight the potential of the catalog for investigating the global distribution and statistical properties of small lunar impact craters.

Implications: The developing catalog provides a valuable resource for future investigations of lunar impact processes, small-impactor populations in the Earth–Moon system, and crater-based surface age dating at sub-kilometer scales [10]. The dataset may also support studies of lunar regolith evolution and surface modification processes [11]. A detailed description of the detection methodology, dataset characteristics, and spatial statistics is currently under review for publication.

Figure 1. Spatial Distribution of Lunar Impact Craters: Grid-Based Statistical Analysis. This figure presents the spatial distribution of lunar impact craters using a grid-based statistical approach. Each $1^\circ \times 1^\circ$ grid cell displays the total count of cataloged craters within that region. Warm colors (yellow-orange-red) indicate high crater density areas, while cool colors (blue-cyan) represent lower densities. Peak grid values are labeled with crater counts. Cyan boundaries delineate lunar maria regions [12]. The color scale uses PowerNorm transformation ($\gamma=0.5$) to enhance contrast in low-value areas.

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